

The Practical and Social Importance of Art in The Spiritual and Moral Form of the Person

AUTHOR(S): IFTIKHOR BAKHTIYOROVICH KAMOLOV
AND
NAZIRA ARZIYEVA

Abstract

This article discusses the role of art, especially the visual arts, in the development and perfection of the human person. Fine art is about the emergence, growth and social and practical significance of aesthetic thinking, which can contribute to the spiritual, moral and cultural development of the individual, and the spiritual and moral formation of the individual.

Keywords: aesthetic thinking, color expressions, creativity, talent,

IJARBAS

Accepted 25 April 2021
Published 30 April 2021
DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.4739273

About Author

Author(s): Iftikhor Bakhtiyorovich Kamolov

PhD, Karshi State University
Head of the Department of Fine Arts
and engineering graphics, Uzbekistan.

Nazira Arziyeva

Master's student of Karshi State University, Uzbekistan.

Art provides knowledge, can illuminate even the most fundamental parts of human thinking, allows for a brighter understanding of the world through figurative philosophical expression of words, sounds, colors. The power of art, including fine art, lies in the fact that it can bring any particular work to a universal, perfect level. The role of fine arts in solving the problem of forming the spiritual and moral values of students is invaluable. In the process of its activity, the fine arts have the power of influences that nurture and develop the essence of beautification of the student's own inner and outer world, in which the student seeks to shape himself.

The neglect of art, the only field of human activity aimed at the spiritual and moral formation of people, leads to indifference to spiritual, moral development.

Throughout all periods of human life, the role of art has always been and will always be to reflect life in beautiful forms, to improve it, to direct people's hearts to truth, goodness and beauty. Conveying your worldview, striving for the beauties of life, rejecting evil and striving to get rid of it and liberate others is the beginning, in which case art is not art and the artist is not an artist.

No matter how feelings, attitudes, and beliefs change, the truth remains the same without change, and sooner or later it will inevitably manifest in all its glory. Classical art means believing in the perfection of the world and striving to restore this lost perfection, purifying the hearts of people, inspired by the lofty call of man. Mankind has created and maintained high moral and aesthetic values in this complex, conflicting, but necessary area of spiritual life - art.

Fine art covers all spheres of life, it is inextricably linked with science, labor and education. Aesthetic education is not a measure of the information that is added to education, but a self-education, an action that develops a person's emotions and his creative abilities. Lack of understanding of the importance and place of fine arts in the life of society is one of the main signs of aesthetic and moral underdevelopment of people. Everyone should understand the role and importance of fine arts in the development of society. This requires a spiritual culture and a clear moral standard. Fine art imitates simple tastes, calls it "modern," imitates true creativity, wears the mask of contemplation, and interprets lies as truth, or vice versa. A person who is not accustomed to figurative thinking since childhood, who does not know the basics of understanding art, cannot understand himself.

The need for fine arts is a constant feature of the human heart. An individual's independent thinking, indifference to the development of fine arts, indifference to works of art, and unpreparedness for artistic perception of works lead to a departure from true culture and morality.

Cognition in the fine arts is the product of the interaction of knowledge and imagination, they do not deny each other, but unite in the highest synthesis of artistic truth ... Nothing else can affect the human psyche like an image. Awakening the imagination, reaching the heart, making one think, fine art purifies and elevates one. Therefore, the school curriculum for teaching fine arts is of particular importance.

Adequate content of education is also necessary for the development of a harmoniously developed person.

This can be achieved by giving the visual arts a worthy role in the educational process. Fine art contributes to fostering truly creative thinking. It increases the need for labor, teaches people to enjoy works of art created by useful and beautiful human hands.

The importance of spiritual and moral education in school was shaped in 1919 by well-known experts, scholars and teachers: "In general, aesthetic education is not about teaching

children some simplified art, but about enjoying beauty and the systematic development of perceptions and creative abilities that expand the possibilities of creation must be understood. Without this element, labor and scientific education would be soulless, for the joy of life from wonder and creativity is the ultimate goal of both labor and science” (MA Savitsky).

“Leading moral education means creating an ethical tone of school life, which is expressed in the fact that every student cares about someone and cares about someone, giving their heart to someone.” V.A. Suxomlinskiy

Reflecting on the words of the great Master, you realize that the values of the past have been replaced by other spiritual guidelines: goodness, truth, and beauty are gradually being pushed to the margins of life. The political and socio-economic changes taking place in our country have had a serious impact on all aspects of people's lives and activities, which creates the basis for strengthening the attention paid to the national, spiritual and moral development of the younger generation.

Modern youth are “spending a lot of time” in a confined space with television or computers, and the influx of products that promote unhealthy lifestyles is one of the main reasons for the decline in violence, crime, and moral and ethical standards. The child knows how to perceive the world only with his eyes and ears, and the rest of his emotions are processed separately.

In order to awaken the understanding, thinking, moral thoughts and other feelings of the younger generation, it is necessary to acquaint them with art: music, literature, painting, theater. This is how children know the origin of culture, morality, spirituality.

Understanding moral norms, assimilating spiritual values and moral principles can happen spontaneously and purposefully. The process of moral formation of personality, as a rule, takes place on three levels:

- (1) understanding and studying ethical norms and principles;
- (2) the transformation of moral norms into the moral convictions of the individual;
- (3) have the skills and abilities to apply this knowledge and beliefs, as well as moral behavioral habits, in a creative way in practice.

The first level of formation of a person's moral consciousness - the understanding and study of moral norms and principles - is provided by the study of the rules of ethics in educational institutions, in the system of formal training and advanced training in the classroom. Before that, moral knowledge is acquired spontaneously, sometimes conditionally, in the environment around us - in the family, at school, in the circle of friends and acquaintances, and so on. However, this knowledge alone is not enough for a person to have a moral culture. The immediate environment is able to create the necessary conditions for the proper moral formation of the individual, to lay its foundation in the form of knowledge about “what is good and what is bad”.

The transformation of moral norms into human moral beliefs begins at the secondary level, and when the acquired knowledge becomes a moral belief, they do not bypass the boundaries of morality because they are convinced that it is impossible to act, not because one knows. ... Art, including the visual arts, plays a very important role in the second level of the moral formation of the individual.

With the most diversity and versatility of the concept of fine art, it is the field of human activity in its most general form. Fine art involves the creation of objects of aesthetic importance - works of art, as well as conveying them to the public through their inclusion in

the process of public communication. The artist creates a work of art and reflects some aspects of reality. V.G. Belinskiy.

"Knowledge of art, a developed aesthetic sense is a condition of human dignity ..."

At the same time, he always portrays her in terms of his moral position.

Thus, the artist chooses the method of illuminating the truth and tends the viewer (reader, listener) to this or that moral value.

It looks aesthetically beautiful in a morally perfect art. This, of course, does not mean that ethical issues end the content of art. The relationship between morality and art is manifested in a more complex form.

In short, the knowledge of fine art, its artistic and emotional perception, the developed aesthetic sense is a condition of human dignity: only with it can reason be understood, only with it can the scientist ascend to the ideas of the world ... only thus the citizen can do his work from the yacht and does not bend under its own weight. Without it, there is no sense, no genius, no talent, no intellect - only the perfect "common sense" needed for housework, for the little calculations of selfishness.

References:

- Камолов, И. Б. (2020). Особенности развития творческих способностей студентов в процессе профессионального образования. *Молодой ученый*, (10), 136-138.
- Камолов, И. Б. ФОРМИРОВАНИЕ У УЧАЩИХСЯ УМЕНИЯ ПРЕПОДАВАТЬ ЮВЕЛИРНЫЕ УРОКИ. СЕКЦИЯ ЛАР: «ПЕДАГОГИКАЛЫҚ КАДРЛАРДЫ ДАЯРЛАУ ЖҮЙЕСІН ЖАҢҒЫРТУ» «ПСИХОЛОГИЯ» «ӨНЕРТАНУ» СЕКЦИИ, 21.
- Kamolov, I. B. "PROFESSIONAL EDUCATION OF STUDENTS STUDYING JEWELRY: THE THEORETIC BASIS." *SCIENCE AND WORLD* (2013): 69.
- Kamolov, I. B. (2016). MAJOR COMPONENTS AND TOPICS OF DISCIPLINES ACCORDING TO THE COMPOSITION OF JEWELRY AS A PEDAGOGICAL OBJECTIVE OF THE CREATIVE DEVELOPMENT OF COLLEGE ART STUDENTS. *European Journal of Research and Reflection in Educational Sciences Vol, 4(2)*.
- Kamolov, I. B. (2017). Some Stages Associated with Artistic and Creative Activity of Future Jeweler. *Eastern European Scientific Journal*, (1).
- Шадиёв, Р. Д., & Камолов, И. Б. (2014). Педагогическая модель профессионального образования в ювелирном искусстве: основные параметры концепции. *Austrian Journal of Humanities and Social Sciences*, (11-12).
- Камолов, И. Б. "Профессиональное образование учащихся ювелирного искусства: теоретические основы." *Наука и Мир* 3.2 (2016): 68-69.
- Olimov, Shirinboy Sharofovich. "THE INNOVATION PROCESS IS A PRIORITY IN THE DEVELOPMENT OF PEDAGOGICAL SCIENCES." (2021).

Cite this article:

Author(s), IFTIKHOR BAKHTIYOROVICH KAMOLOV, NAZIRA ARZIYEVA, (2021). “The Practical and Social Importance of Art in The Spiritual and Moral Form of the Person”. Name of the Journal: International Journal of Academic Research in Business, Arts and Science, (IJARBAS.COM), P, 27- 32. DOI: <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4739273> , Issue: 4, Vol.: 3, Article: 4, Month: April, Year: 2021. Retrieved from <https://www.ijarbas.com/all-issues/>

Published by

AND

ThoughtWares Consulting & Multi Services International (TWCMSI)

